
The effect of welding parameters on interface temperature and mechanical properties for ultrasonic welding of flax/polypropylene composite without energy director

Oussama EL-OGRI, Laurence SERREAU, Jérôme ROUSSEAU

DRIVE laboratory, Bourgogne Franche-Comté University, Nevers, France

Outline

Context and objective

Methodology

Ultrasonic welding

Conclusion & Outlooks

Introduction

Welding of thermoplastic composites

Ultrasonic welding

Study objectives

Automobile, Sports, Building...

Urban furniture...

Differing in how heat is generated at the interface

Thermal

Hot plate welding

Hot gaz welding

Infrared welding

Laser welding

External heat input to the interfaces

Contacting the 2 surfaces under pressure

Electromagnetic

Induction welding

Dielectric welding

Micro-wave welding

Resistance welding

Interface heating by an high-frequency field

Contacting the 2 surfaces under pressure

Friction

Friction stir welding

Vibration welding

Ultrasonic welding

Rotational welding

Friction at the interface

Pressure cooling

Piezoelectric converter 2

Converts electrical energy into mechanical energy

Pneumatic actuator

Sonotrode 4

Transmits mechanical energy to the part

3 Booster

Amplifies mechanical energy

Displacement sensor

1 Frequency generator

Converts electrical energy from 50/60 Hz to 20 kHz

Upper workpiece

Lower workpiece

Context and objective

Materials and methods

Ultrasonic welding

Conclusion and outlooks

Introduction

Welding of thermoplastic composites

Ultrasonic welding

Study objectives

Analyzing the influence of ultrasonic welding parameters on the mechanical properties and temperature profiles generated during the welding process

Determining the optimal ultrasonic welding parameters for thermoplastic composites reinforced with flax fibers

Achieving strong welds and enhancing the reliability of the welding process

Context and objective

Methodology

Ultrasonic welding

Conclusion & Outlooks

Lincore Flax/PP

Manufacturing process

Ultrasonic welding

Characterisation

LINCORE® PP FF P2 40 400

Depestele

PP : Polypropylene matrix

FF : Flax fabrics

T2 : Twill 2/2

40 : Flax content in weight (%)

440 : Nominal weight (g/m²)

PP matrix

➤ Semi-crystalline

➤ $T_f = 150 \text{ à } 170 \text{ °C}$

Twill 2/2

Lincore Flax/PP

Manufacturing process

Ultrasonic welding

Characterisation

Thermocompression

200 °C, 3 min

Lincore Flax/PP

Manufacturing process

Ultrasonic welding

Characterisation

Pneumatic machine Herrmann
20 kHz – 3600 W

Rectangular
sonotrode
25 x 40 mm²

Clamp
fixation

Anvil

Time mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Welding time ✓ Welding force ✓ Amplitude (35 μm) ✓ Consolidation time (2s) ✓ Consolidation force
Energy mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Energy ✓ Welding force ✓ Amplitude (35 μm) ✓ Consolidation time (2s) ✓ Consolidation force
Displacement mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Displacement ✓ Welding force ✓ Amplitude (35 μm) ✓ Consolidation time (2s) ✓ Consolidation force

Overlapped area
25 x 15 mm²

100 mm

3,1

25 mm

Lincore Flax/PP

Manufacturing process

Ultrasonic welding

Characterisation

➤ Temperature measurement

Lincore Flax/PP

Manufacturing process

Ultrasonic welding

Characterisation

➤ Mechanical testing : Lap shear strength (LSS)

ASTM D1002

2 mm/min

Misaligned
jaws

$$LSS1 = \frac{\text{Peak load}}{\text{Total overlap area}}$$

LSS1 quantifies
the effectiveness
of the joint

$$LSS2 = \frac{\text{Peak load}}{\text{Effective welded area}}$$

LSS2 defines the
weld quality

Context and objective

Methodology

Ultrasonic welding

Conclusion & Outlooks

Thermal analysis

Temperature profile

Amplitude = 35 μm

Welding time = 500 ms

Welding force = 400 N

Consolidation time = 2000 ms

Consolidation force = 400 N

- ① Heating at 2500 $^{\circ}\text{C/s}$
- ② PP flow
- ③ End of vibration
- ④ Cooling at 600 $^{\circ}\text{C/s}$

Lap-shear-strength

Fractography analysis

Thermal analysis

Lap-shear-strength

Fractography analysis

Thermal analysis

Lap-shear-strength

Fractography analysis

Welding time

Expulsion

Unwelded area

Darkened area
Fibre deformation

Under-welded

Good-welded

Over-welded

Thermal analysis

Lap-shear-strength

Fractography analysis

➤ Welding time

Thermal analysis

Lap-shear-strength

Fractography analysis

Welding force

Under-welded

Good-welded

Under-welded

Thermal analysis

Lap-shear-strength

Fractography analysis

➤ Welding force

200 N

420 N

Context and objective

Methodology

Ultrasonic welding

Conclusion & Outlooks

Conclusion

- ❑ Understanding the impact of parameters on temperature profile and mechanical strength of welds

Welding time

- The mechanical strength increases with the welding time
- Threshold : Burning of Flax Fiber

Welding force

- The mechanical strength increases with the welding force
- Threshold : absence of vibration

- ❑ Acquiring strong and reproducible welds

- ❑ Two optimal welding conditions:
 - 700 ms - 35 m - 400 N
 - 500 ms - 35 m - 420 N

Outlooks

- ❖ Study of physicochemical changes induced by the process (oxidation of fibers and matrix, modification of crystallinity)
- ❖ Comparison between time mode, energy mode and displacement mode
- ❖ Study of the effect of an energy director